

BINODINI - A JOURNEY OF A WOMAN FROM KOTHA TO RANGAMANCHA

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Biographical or autobiographical plays are not very popular here. But Binodini Dasi (1863-1941), better known as Nati Binodini is an exception. Plays on Binodini's life and career have been staged over and over for a long time now mainly because the story of her life is more dramatic than the ones we read in fiction and has more twists and turns than a film script. The 'Nati' in her name means 'actress'. Binodini carved an immortal place in the history of Bengali theatre not only for her talent and her versatility as an actress, but also for the sacrifices she made in the cause of theatre, her first love. She documented the story of her life in two separate autobiographies, *Aamar Katha* (My story) and *Aamar Abhinetri Jeebon* (My life as an actress). Perhaps the autobiographical plays also made the viewer draw parallels between a woman's life as an actress and her life as a woman deprived of the experiences of mainstream womanhood where the two worlds sometimes meet, overlap and then part, never to meet again. Does this hold true of the actress of today?

As she read what she has written, the past unfolds different layers of her life, segments from plays she has performed in, her interactions with her mother, a prostitute who forced her daughter to become a mistress, her relationship with her guru and mentor, the famous Girish Chandra Ghosh, and her constant conflicts between her personal and professional life forced on her by none other than her peers on the stage and by her mentor himself. The present paper aims to visualize again her life, her workings, and the writings of Nati Binodini with the context of sociological background of other female artists of Bengal Theatre in the present context.

Key words: Binodini, *Kotha*, *Rangamancha*

Introduction:

Kolkata is the seat of performing arts in this part of the world. Kolkata's citizens love music and theatre and they thrive in the city in various ways. Kolkata's discerning audience is appreciated by performers making it a popular venue for large concerts. Kolkata's citizens' passion for music is arguably best represented by the countless home-run schools of music that have mushroomed in the residential neighborhoods. Even before modern theatre arrived in Kolkata, Bengal had its own theatrical tradition in the *jatra*, an open air theater. The *jatra* season begins after the monsoons and ends with summer, with groups participating from all parts of Eastern India and Bangladesh. Modern theatre was introduced to Kolkata in the nineteenth century by a Russian nobleman by the name of Lebedoff, although the first European theatre existed in what was then known as Tank Square and is now known as Dalhousie Square in the 1770s. The local Bengali population already addicted to *jatra* took to theatre like ducks to water. Star Theater was established on College Street soon after with actors like Girish Ghosh and actresses like Nati Binodini. The historical Star Theatre burnt down some years ago, a most unfortunate accident, by all means. Theaters include the Girish Mancha in Bagbazar, the Sisir Mancha on Lower Circular Road and the Nazrul Mancha in the Dakshinapan Complex, besides the classical Rangana Theatre in Shyambazar and the usual auditoriums.

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As she read what she has written, the past unfolds different layers of her life, segments from plays she has performed in, her interactions with her mother, a prostitute who forced her daughter to become a mistress, her relationship with her *guru* and mentor, the famous Girish Chandra Ghosh, and her constant conflicts between her personal and professional life forced on her by none other than her peers on the stage and by her mentor himself. When Binodini was performing in *Sri Chaitanya* in the title role of the *Vaishnava* saint, Sri Sri Paramhansa walked up to the stage after

watching the play, placed his hand on Binodini's head and blessed her. From that time on, Binodini gradually began to withdraw from the stage and finally quit after dominating the Bengali stage from 1873 to 1887. She married a local zamindar -- popularly known as *Ranga Babu*, a nickname -- who was patiently waiting in the wings and the couple also bore a daughter, *Shakuntala*. According to Devajit Bandopadhyaya, widely known as the best living scholar on Bengali theatre and its music, the descendants of this zamindar are still alive and are political leaders and powerful people. *Shakuntala* died when she was only 11, the age when Binodini had stepped on the stage for the first time as an extra. Soon after, her husband and benefactor also passed away when Binodini was in her mid-thirties, leaving her alone and isolated, with memories to lean back on till her death.

Theatre in Bengal:

Theater is one of the oldest forms of performing art. From the stone ages, men and women have been telling stories by enacting them when even no language existed. The British rule having established itself, the English plays began being performed from 1785 onwards. In that year Russian citizen Gerasim Lebedoff came to India in his pursuit of learning Indian languages and settled down in Kolkata. He translated two English plays and seeking cooperation of actors-actresses of Kolkata he started dramatic activity in 1795. Bengali people's love for drama received further fillip when from London the famous actor David Sorick sent his drama company to Kolkata and the company staged plays by Sheridan and Shakespeare in Calcutta theaters. Bengali folk drama forms '*Jatra*', '*Jatra Kirtaniya*', and '*Pala-Gan*' have always been performed in the open grounds in the villages of Bengal and even today this practice of folk-dramas continues. The contribution of these folk-drama forms is indeed very big and significant in nurturing the love for drama among the Bengali people. Subsequent to 1795 the professional theaters came to be established in Bengal of which Vidyasundar Drama Theater commanded attention. Madhusudan Dutta and Dinobandhu Mitra were outstanding Bengali playwrights. Their play '*Neeldarpan*' staged in 1860 had as its theme the rebellion of the workers. Thereafter the great actor-director-poet Girishchandra Ghosh gave a big impetus to the drama movement and was rightly called the builder of Bengali Rangbhoomi. The playwright Dwijendralal Roy (1813-1913) made a mark as a very talented writer of historical dramas imbued with love for the motherland and nationalist spirit. The plays were written for the professional theater. Prof. Shishir Bhaduri was a talented dramatist, a great artist of voice control, and an actor who could perform a gamut of characters with great facility. He has rightly been called the saviour of Bengali theatre. In the recent times, the dramatists Ahindra Chowdhury, Shambhu Mitra and Trupti Mitra have made unique contributions to the progress of the Bengali drama. Utpal Dutta has been a much-honoured name in the development of Bengali theatrical arts, his '*Angaar*' play being a major achievement.

Tapas Sen., a great craftsman in light-effects has earned world recognition for himself and for India. In this period '*Bahurupi*' and "Indian People's Theater" stand out among countless Bengali theater groups for their most significant plays. Trupti Mitra besides being a highly talented actress set up her own theater group which attracted many new young actors-actresses and taking them together with her, she presented some of the best plays of Kalidas and Bhavbhooti on the Bengali stage. Thus in the development of modern Indian drama the contribution of the Bengali Theater is indeed very great and today also it continues its forward movement towards the future.

Women in Bengal Theatre:

The professional Bengal theatre started on 7th December. 1872 with the play '*Neeldarpan*' in National Theatre. At that time there were no actresses - only male artists. Male artists were doing female roles also. But after one or two years female artists had come in Bengal theatre. But at that time all the actresses had come from brothels. There were too much problems, discussions, nasty talking, showing of fear and muscle power there, but in spite all of these, they retained there with their talents and patience. Within few years it was recognized that without them it was impossible to carrying on the Bengal theatre. Bengal theatre was started first by Russian citizen Gerasim Lebedoff. He himself translated the English play '*Disguise*' into Bengali and it was on stage on 27th November. 1795. In this play three 'real' female artists had acted. They had also come from brothels or some others historian said they had come from the group of '*jhumur*' or '*kirtaniya*'. However, it is clear that female artists were there from the early era of Bengal theatre. Again on 6th December. 1835, '*Vidyasundar*' was on stage. Here also three female artists had acted. There was Radhamani as '*Vidya*', Joydurga as '*Rani*' and '*Malini*', Rajkumari or Raju a '*Sakhi*'.

Not only in theatre were women good also in Bengal *jatras*. In 1849 they acted in many *jatras*. '*Nandabiday Jatra*' was one of them where female artists were acted. So it is very surprising that whenever the female artists had acted in theatre or in *jatras* they were given immense enthusiasm. But it was not the last word. There were many difficulties also. Many historians, theatre critics were opposite of this acts. They thought it would pollute the Bengali culture. Many newspapers also were opposed these. '*Hindu Patriot*' had quoted on 18th august. 1873, ".....The actors performed their parts very creditably, the two actresses, who were professional women, we were informed, were most

successful. but we had hoped that the managers of Bengali theatres would not bring themselves down to the level of the *jatrawallas*." But whatever may be, the contribution of female artists on that time was, no doubt, the beginning of a new era of theatre actress which was started from Lebedoff three female artists.

Some Women Theatre Personalities at That Time:

There were many women theatre personalities at that time. Among them Sukumari Devi, Tinkari Devi, Kusumkumari Devi, Tarasundari Devi, Binodini Dasi were most famous. There were many others lead actresses and part actresses were there who enlightend the Bengali Theatre very much.

Nati Binodini: *

Binodini Dasi (1862 -1941) also known as Nati Binodini was a Calcutta based Bengali speaking renowned actress and thespian. Born to prostitution, she started her career as a courtesan and at 12 she played her first serious drama role in Calcutta's National Theatre in 1874. Her career coincided with the popularity of the proscenium inspired form of European theatre among the Bengali theater going audience. During a career spanning 12 years she enacted over 80 roles. Her roles included those of Promila, Sita, Draupadi, Radha, Ayesha, Kaikeyi, Motibibi, and Kapalkundala among others. She was one of the first South Asian actresses of the theater to write her own autobiography. Her sudden retirement from the stage is insufficiently explained. As a leading actress she was passionately devoted to the development of theatre in Bengal. She made monetary contributions to build up the once famous Star Theatre in Calcutta, which she wanted to be named after her. In her autobiography, she has admitted to the fact that in order to help procure funds for the Star Theatre and its company, she agreed to become the mistress of a rich businessman for some time.

Sri Ramakrishna, the great saint of Advaita Vedanta came to see her play in 1884, and visited Binodini backstage afterwards - an event which left a deep impression on the actress who became an ardent devotee of Ramakrishna soon after. During her bygone days of glory, she was referred to as the " *Flower of the Native Stage* " and the " *Moon of the Star Theatre* ". She was a pioneering entrepreneur of the Bengali stage and introduced modern techniques of stage make-up through blending European and indigenous styles. Her autobiography is lucid and explores a section of the 19th century Bengali world, at ease with European ideas, but conscious enough to carefully subjugate the female to the domain of the household. Women who talked of and expressed in their lives the very embodiment of liberated femininity were, surreptitiously viewed from a distance, to be loved and be the object of scorn -- and never aspire to respectable notions of femininity.

Family Background of Binodini

The family background of Binodini was not so graceful at all. She was from a poor family. As told in *AAMAR KATHA*, the autobiography of Binodini, she lived at 145 no. house in Cornwallis Street. At that place there lived some other poor tenants also. She lived there with her grandmother, mother & her brother. They were at that time so poor that they had to sell their ornaments to fulfill their daily requirements. She lost her brother at that childhood. After his brother's death her mother became little mentally imbalanced. When her age was near 9 years, one female singer came to their house & she started to live there. Her name was Ganga Baiji. That Ganga Baiji later became a famous singer of Star Theatre. However, she lived on the 1st floor of that house. That Ganga Baiji lived there very happily and she remembered it till the last day of her life. Binodini and Ganga Baiji called one another by the name of "Golap". Later that Ganga Baiji was given the name Gangamani when she became famous.

Binodini at first started to learn song from that Gangamani. After her brother's death two men used to come to Gangamani's room for listening songs. They were Punachandra Mukherjee and Brojonath Seth. After watching their miserable days they first gave Binodini's mother a proposal for joining of Binodini in theatre. At that time they told to her mother that if she would join the theatre then it would be good for the economical part of their family and with that when she would learn the job well she would get comparatively more salary than she would get at that moment. So that's was the starting of an eminent theater artist of our Bengal. At that time there was two main theater halls in Calcutta. One was National Theatre of Sri Bhuvanmohon Neogi and another was Bengal Theater of Sri Saratchandra Ghosh. Binodini joined at National Theater with the salary of Rupees 10 per month. That was the family background and as well as her childhood. She came to theater from a miserable life and she joined the Bengali theatre mainly for her family or more precisely to run the family.

Acting Life of Binodini

The acting life as Binodini was only of 12 years (2nd or 12th December 1874 – 1st January 1887). Within these time she was conjugated with four stage theatres:

- a) Great National Theatre > (December 1874 – April 1876)

- b) Bengal Theatre > (April 1876 – August 1877)
 c) Great National Theatre > (October 1877)
 d) National Theatre > (1st December 1877 – 4th February 1883)
 e) Star Theatre > (21st July 1883 – 1st January 1887)

At that time these stage theatres were going on with many ups and down and changeable position of their ownerships. For that reason it was sometime inevitable to take temporary retirements from the stage. It was not exceptional for Binodini also. However, here I am presenting a brief acting life history of Binodini according to her appearance on the stage with her characters, name of the plays throughout her life year wise.

Year Wise & Theatre Wise Selected Acting Works of Binodini

Great National Theatre

<u>Date</u>	<u>Name of the Play</u>	<u>Character</u>
2 nd /12 th Dec. 1874	<i>Shatrusanhara</i>	<i>Sakhi of Draupadi</i>
6 th March. 1875	<i>Hemlata</i>	<i>Hemlata</i>
April. 1875	<i>Sati ki Kalankini?</i>	<i>Radhika</i>
April. 1875	<i>Sadhabar Ekadoshi</i>	<i>Kanchan</i>
May. 1875	<i>Neeldarpan</i>	<i>Saralata</i>
8 th January. 1876	<i>Prokito Bondhu</i>	<i>Banamala</i>
15 th January. 1876	<i>Sarojini</i>	<i>Sarojini</i>

Bengal Theatre

24 th March. 1877	<i>Meghnadbadh</i>	<i>Pramila</i>
16 th April. 1877	<i>Mrinalini</i>	<i>Monorama</i>
18 th April. 1877	<i>Kapalkundala</i>	<i>Kapalkundala</i>

National Theatre

5 th January. 1878	<i>Juddha</i>	<i>Britannia</i>
27 th April. 1878	<i>Bishabrikhya</i>	<i>Kundannandini</i>
22 nd June. 1878	<i>Durgeshnandini</i>	<i>Aayasha</i>
1 st January. 1881	<i>Hameer</i>	<i>Leela</i>
15 th January. 1881	<i>Meghnadbadh</i>	<i>Rati, Maya Sita, Promila</i>
22 nd January. 1881	<i>Mayataru</i>	<i>Phulhasi</i>
9 th April. 1881	<i>Mohini Protima</i>	<i>Sahana</i>
30 th July. 1881	<i>Rabanbadh</i>	<i>Sita</i>
26 th February. 1882	<i>Neeldarpan</i>	<i>Saralata</i>
15 th April. 1882	<i>Ramer Banobas</i>	<i>Kailae</i>
22 nd July. 1882	<i>Sita Haran</i>	<i>Sita</i>

Star Theatre

21 st July. 1883	<i>Dakkhyajanggya</i>	<i>Sati</i>
11 th August. 1883	<i>Dhrubacharitra</i>	<i>Suruchi</i>
15 th December. 1883	<i>Naladamayanti</i>	<i>Damayanti</i>
29 th March. 1884	<i>Kamalekamini</i>	<i>Chandi, Khullana</i>
26 th April. 1884	<i>Heerar Phul</i>	<i>Shashikala</i>
26 th April. 1884	<i>Brishaketu</i>	<i>Padyabati</i>
2 nd August. 1884	<i>Chaitanyaleela</i>	<i>Nimai (Chaitanya)</i>
22 nd November. 1884	<i>Bibahabivrata</i>	<i>Bilasini, Karforma</i>
25 th March. 1885	<i>Mrinalini</i>	<i>Monorama</i>
30 th May. 1885	<i>Provash Janggya</i>	<i>Satyabhama</i>
19 th September. 1885	<i>Buddhadeb Charita</i>	<i>Gopa</i>
7 th October. 1885	<i>Chaitanyaleela</i>	<i>Nimai (Chaitanya)</i>

12th June. 1886
26th December. 1886
1st January. 1887
1st January. 1887

<i>Billyamangal Thakur</i>	<i>Chintamani</i>
<i>Bellickbazar</i>	<i>Rangini</i>
<i>Naladamayanti</i>	<i>Damayanti</i>
<i>Bellickbazar</i>	<i>Rangini</i>

Apart from these plays Binodini Also acted in many plays and in various characters. Among those some plays are:

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|---------------------------|------------------------------|
| 1) <i>Biye pagal Buro</i> | 6) <i>Aadarshasati</i> |
| 2) <i>Leelabati</i> | 7) <i>Belbabu ka tamasha</i> |
| 3) <i>Vidyasundar</i> | 8) <i>Sarat-Sarojini</i> |
| 4) <i>Aagomani</i> | 9) <i>Akbar</i> |
| 5) <i>Dolleela</i> | 10) <i>Laxman Barjan</i> |

In some of her plays we cannot find the specific role of her which she had played on that play. Some of them are:

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|---------------------------|------------------------|
| 1) <i>Bijoya</i> | 6) <i>Malinmala</i> |
| 2) <i>Jhakmarir Masul</i> | 7) <i>Votemangal</i> |
| 3) <i>Kaminikunja</i> | 8) <i>Kaliodaman</i> |
| 4) <i>Jenana Juddha</i> | 9) <i>Tiltarpan</i> |
| 5) <i>Aanantashayan</i> | 10) <i>Promodkanan</i> |

After watching the “*Chaitanyaleela*”, Colonel H. S. Olcott (1828–1907) told, “As for the *Chaitanyaleela*, I unhesitatingly affirm that it is impossible for anyone to witness the play without a rush of spiritual feeling and religious favour. The poor girl who played ‘*Chaitanya*’ may belong to the class of unfortunates, but while on the scene she throws herself into her role so ardently that one only sees the Vaishnava saint before him.”

Star Theatre and Binodini

Standing on the peak of popularity and prosperity and leaving all the possibility towards her successful life Nati Binodini took the self retirement from the theatre life. There was some defined reason behind her retiredness. As told in ‘*Aamar Katha*’, by Binodini herself that there were some specific reasons behind that. One of those was deception to her by Girishchandra and associates about Star Theatre. When the theatre company that took Binodini to starry heights began to collapse, in 1883, her mentor persuaded her to become the mistress of Gurmukh Rai, a rich Marwari businessman who was a devoted fan of Binodini. The actress, hating to go back to her old life of prostitution, rejected the idea. But her love for the stage and empathy for her peers whose lives were endangered, won in the end and she succumbed to pressure. Instead of accepting a cheque for Rs.50,000 from Rai, Binodini asked him to build a theatre hall.

Rai, besotted with Binodini, agreed at once, but on condition that the theatre hall would be named B-Theatre, after the first letter of Binodini's name. Yet, when the time came, the members of the group did not keep this promise. After the theatre's name was registered, Binodini was shocked to discover that her name was rejected in favour of another name, Star, in 1884. Her peers and mentor had decided that a theatre house named after a prostitute would fail to draw audience for their plays. Gurmukh Rai also wanted to give some part of ownership of right of Star to Binodini but they also swindled that. Binodini had written out it in her autobiography and often entered into a discourse with the ghost of Girishchandra Ghosh, her teacher and mentor, the historic personality of the Bengali stage, on a wheelchair. The wheelchair was a metaphor for Ghosh whose theatre was almost crippled after Binodini left.

From that time on, Binodini gradually began to withdraw from the stage and finally quit after dominating the Bengali stage from 1873 to 1887. After the making of Star Theatre, Girishchandra lobby didn't allow Binodini to act on the stage of Star also. At that time she had to wait for two months in her home without any acting works, though she was a full-timer permanent artist of Star Theatre. After that she came sometime in Star Theatre but not as an actress but as an audience.

Writings of Binodini

Binodini had showed her capability in writings also. Though her writings works had not made so popular by her so called well wishers at that time but as time run it was automatically popularized among her fan and theatre lovers. Her life is indeed a play in today's theatre. Whatever it is found till date is given here.....

1. Serial letters about stage theatre in the newspaper, ‘*Bharatbasi*’ in the year of 1885.
2. Three poems (‘*Hridayratna*’, ‘*Aabosaad*’, and ‘*Aabha*’) in the newspaper ‘*Sourav*’, which was included later in the book ‘*Basana*’ in the year of 1892.

3. 'Basana', a collection of 41 poems in the year of 1893.
4. 'Kanaka and Nalini', a poems cum story in the year of 1902.
5. 'Aabhinetrir Aatyakatha', published in newspaper, 'Naty Mandir', edited by Aamarendra Tagore in the year of 1907.
6. 'Aamar Katha', 1st part, 1st Edition, in the year of 1909.
7. 'Binodinir Katha' or 'Aamar Katha', published by Sri Gurudas Chatterjee in the year of 1910.
8. 'Aamar Abhinetri Jeebon', published in the newspaper 'Rup o Rango', edited by Saratchandra Chatterjee and Nirmalchandra Chandra, in the years between 1921 and 1922. It was published serially either in the name of 'Aabhinetrir Aatyakatha' or in the name of 'Aamar Abhinetri Jeebon'. It was incomplete.

Binodini on Record

The Gramophone Company came here in the beginning of the 20th century. *Kaler Gaan*, The miracle invention of science, naturally was being very much popular to the nation. In these records, apart from songs, there were recording of speeches also of famous and popular personalities. To hear the popular songs and with it the popular plays by these records had made them so popular. In the case of Binodini also there was no exception.

But there exist some controversy with it for Binodini. The visual theatres of Binodini are very much real to us. But for the recordings of her via record is little bit suspicious. The main reason behind that is at that time there was a famous singer named Binodini. It is written upon all the songs records the name "Dasi Binodini". But it is written upon all the Playing records the name "Miss Binodini". And also the word "late" was written in the record-list of 1920 of Gramophone Company before the name of Binodini Dasi. But for "Miss Binodini", no "late" was written even on the record of 1930. Here also one thing all the recordings were found only with disk of Gramophone Company not with the Zonophone Company, who was also entered in India's market. Whether the records of "Miss Binodini" belongs to Nati Binodini, the another controversy was at the time there was one more "Binodini" on the stage theatre. But of her case all time the word "*Handi*" was written in the bracket after her name and she was not so beautiful and was not also so good actress. So here is the question, why The Gramophone Company or any other would make record on her, who was not so popular and famous also. There was no possibility for "Binodini (*Handi*)" to hear from Gramophone Company, who came here for their business.

So considering all of these and others evidence from the eye-witness it is very much clear that all the acting records belong to Nati Binodini and all the songs records may belong to singer Binodini or Nati Binodini herself. But if it is true indeed, then all the records found of Binodini not only more, it is much for the Bengali theatre compare to other records here.

Conclusion:

She was not only the "Moon of the Star Company", not only the "Flower of the Native Stage", not only the "Prima Dona of the Bengali Stage" but also she was absolutely at the head of her profession in India. She must be a woman of considerable culture to be able to show such unaffected sympathy with so many and various characters and such capacity of reproducing them. She was certainly a Lady of much refinement of feeling as she shows herself to be one of inimitable grace. Her Mrs. Bilasini Karforma, the girl graduate, exhibited so to say an iron grip of the queer phenomenon, the Girl of the period as she has appeared in Bengali society. Her Chaitanya showed a wonderful mastery of the suitable forces dominating one of the greatest of religious characters that was taken to be the Lord himself and is to this day worshipped as such by millions. For a young Miss to enter into such a being so as to give it perfect expression is a miracle. All we can say that genius faith can remove mountains.

The colorful story of her life, its vicissitudes, dreams and betrayals are set down in her autobiography *Aamar Katha* published in 1319 BS. In the introduction to a recent reprint of the autobiography, Sumitra Chatterjee points out that the chroniclers of the theatre movement in 19th century Bengal are curiously silent on the topic of Binodini Dasi. This may perhaps be due to the fact that in the 19th century, most actresses came from the ranks of prostitutes and Binodini was seen as no exception. Hypocritical standards of the *Bhadrolok* allowed the pleasure derived from theatre viewing, but not an acknowledgement of its actresses. Yet Binodini contributed to the success and development of all the companies she worked with - National, Bengal and Star. In fact the last would not have been founded without her help. Binodini's book is written in an elegant style and here she describes the men and women who taught her, exploited her and loved her. After her retirement she went to live with her protector and benefactor for whom she retained high regard. After his death she lived a quiet lonely life in Calcutta, enlivened by writing and occasional visits to her beloved Star theatre.

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